

INCULTUM

Visiting the margins
INnovative CULtural ToUrisM in European peripheries

INCULTUM final conference, 12th April 2024

Visiting the Margins: Innovative Cultural Tourism in European Peripheries
Community Identity, Tourism as a tool, Innovation

Visitando los márgenes: Turismo cultural innovador en las periferias europeas
Identidad comunitaria, Turismo como herramienta, Innovación

Guadix, 12 April 2024 9,30 - 18,00

ENTURNA Escuela Internacional de Turismo Rural y Naturaleza - Ctra. Murcia s/n Antigua Azucarera

INCULTUM project is an Innovation Action supported by the European Commission in the frame of the Horizon2020 programme, and coordinated by the [University of Granada](#). INCULTUM deals with the challenges and opportunities of cultural tourism with the aim of furthering sustainable social, cultural and economic development.

The final international conference of the INCULTUM project will take place on 12 April, 2024 in Guadix, Andalusia, organised by the University of Granada and hosted by ENTURNA International School of Rural Tourism.

The conference represents a valuable occasion to present results and outcomes of INCULTUM, to prepare for further exploitation by the partners, and to trigger the next implementation and replication phases in new areas across Europe. In this light, the conference will combine know-how and innovation exchange for cultural heritage managers, local administrations, policy makers, researchers, as well as creative and tourism entrepreneurs.

[Read more about the conference](#)

VISITING THE MARGINS: COMMUNITY IDENTITY, TOURISM AS A TOOL, INNOVATION

The ambition of INCULTUM is to transform the concept of cultural tourism from a mere consumer product into a social tool. The innovation of INCULTUM lies in unlocking the potential of cultural tourism to enhance the social, cultural, and economic development of local communities and stakeholders from a sustainable perspective. Ten pilots were developed by the INCULTUM partners, together with stakeholders and communities from nine different countries, covering a variety of geographical contexts, prioritizing remote areas, and valuing cultural and natural heritage. These places narrate the stories of past and present inhabitants, who continue to seek new ways to leverage the potential of their regions, attracting visitors with the authenticity of their traditions. Pilots and partners are presented in a dedicated publication edited by [Promoter srl](#), which is available for free download.

[Download the book](#)

PARTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE AND MODELS IN CULTURE AND CULTURAL TOURISM

The main purpose of the book is to define the key terms of participatory governance in culture. Based on literature review, own knowledge, and experience from previous empirical studies, the authors identify and characterise a range of participatory models that can contribute to value cultural tourism as a part of sustainable development, and demonstrate their application on selected examples of good practices.

The book can serve as inspiration for innovative solutions in cultural policy and cultural tourism development, at the local, regional, national and European level.

This publication is edited by [Matej Bel University](#), and distributed under the licence Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 CC BY-NC.

[Download the book](#)

ONLINE COURSE: MARKETING AND SOCIAL BRANDING IN TOURISM DESTINATIONS

The training course on Marketing and social branding for cultural and sustainable tourism destinations is delivered by the [University of Pisa](#) as an online resource offered to the partners and other users of the INCULTUM Training Portal.

GUIDELINES ON THE USE OF EUROPEAN STRUCTURAL AND INVESTMENT FUNDS

This report is produced by [University of Southern Denmark](#) to analyze the experiences of INCULTUM pilots with European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), providing insights into their application, management, and impact on cultural heritage projects. Three areas of challenges and opportunities are analysed

The goal of the course is to provide the participants with the essentials of marketing logic applied to a cultural and sustainable destination, together with the importance of involving the locals in the place representation and branding. The course highlights the strategic tools for branding processes, from conceptualization to communication and local community involvement.

in the guide, and some recommendations are then illustrated for the use of the managers of the programmes to orientate their policy and fund design, aimed at enhancing the effectiveness, accessibility, and impact of ESIF. The Guidelines are publicly accessible on the [INCULTUM Training Portal](#) and allow the maximum re-usability

[Access Resources](#)

[Read More and Download](#)

MEDIA PARTNER

DIGITAL **CULTURE**

INCULTUM Project Coordinator:
José M^a Martín Civantos
University of Granada
MEMOLab. Laboratorio de Arqueología Biocultural

INCULTUM Network Coordinator:
Antonella Fresa
PROMOTER S.r.l.
Information technology, research and innovation

All images in this newsletter are CC-BY-SA INCULTUM project.

[Contacts](#)

You are receiving this email because your email address is registered in the database of Promoter S.r.l. – DigitalMeetsCulture for one of the following reasons: you joined our network opting in at one of our websites or you have provided freely your consent in the framework of partnerships or other professional relationships or you joined at one of our meetings, events, workshops and similia. Your data will be used exclusively for sending information material related to our network and will not be communicated to any third party. The data controller is Promoter S.r.l., Via della bonifica, 69 - 56037 Peccioli (Pisa) Italy. If you don't want to receive these messages anymore, unsubscribe at the link below.

[unsubscribe for this list](#)

© 2024 Promoter S.r.l.